

Optimizing Task Offloading in Fog-Cloud Computing Environments for Collaborative Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)

*Dinesh Kumar.S¹ and Dr.R.M.S Parvathi²

¹CMS College of Engineering and Technology

²Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Technology

Abstract: *Unmanned aerial vehicles, or UAVs, are employed in a number of tasks, such as emergency response, crowd control, crime prevention, and accident detection. But because UAVs work autonomously, some UAV applications are dynamic and dispersed geographically, necessitating a high degree of real-time computing power. Because of this, processing UAV data locally can be difficult because of their low processing power. Fog and cloud computing can help UAV application development by offering extra resource capacity when needed, hence overcoming such restrictions. It is uncommon in the literature, however, for the construction of complex and effective UAV task offloading algorithms that work with fog and cloud technologies while taking their service latency and energy consumption into account. For this reason, this paper presents a collaborative offloading technique for UAV applications that makes use of the benefits and capabilities of fog and cloud computing. By using this method, UAVs may deliver the necessary resources and services in real time while consuming the least amount of energy and waiting time. Additionally, by allocating compute resources and communication requests from each UAV optimally, task offloading decisions are made using the Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model to minimize the energy consumption of the total UAV-fog-cloud system. When compared to alternative standalone strategies (namely UAV, fog, and cloud), the simulation results show that the proposed strategy can significantly reduce UAV service latency by 15.38%, 35.29%, and 59.26%. It can also reduce overall energy consumption (including processing and networking) by 3.3%, 7.37%, and 12%.*

Keywords: Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), energy efficiency, task offloading, cloud computing, fog computing, cooperative UAVs

I.INTRODUCTION

In several domains, including military, civilian, and industrial uses, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with sensors, cameras, memory, and communication devices are making significant headway as emerging technology. Moreover, because UAVs are widely accessible and reasonably priced, they can be extremely useful in a variety of contexts, including crowd control, monitoring, and logistical support. Furthermore, UAVs have the potential to lower operating costs and dangers while increasing job efficiency (e.g., by lowering the need for human involvement and accessing regions that are challenging for manned vehicles to reach) [1]. Heavy-duty UAVs, on the other hand, generate more processing data and demand more network traffic for tasks like image analysis and video recording. More communication assistance and processing power are therefore needed as a result [2]. Additionally, because of their low computational power, UAV data processing locally is a difficult operation [3]. In this sense, certain computational jobs can be transferred from the UAVs to a cloud server or fog node situated at the network's edge, for distant processing [4]. Both cloud and fog computing offer increased resource capacity and network coverage for UAVs, as well as enable technologies for UAV application development and operation. Although cloud computing can offer effective computing services, data offloading from local UAV devices to a remote cloud and data retrieval from the cloud to the UAVs will result in considerable communication delays [5]. As a result, cloud

computing frequently falls short of meeting the latency-sensitive application, mobility support, and location awareness needs of geo-distributed UAVs and Internet of Things (IoT) sensors. As a result, there is poor Quality of Service (QoS), excessive service latency, and overloaded networks. To bring cloud resources and services closer to UAV devices, an intermediary layer known as fog computing has been created.

During the UAV offloading process, fog computing with adequate processing power can lower service latency [6]. Nevertheless, due to their constrained processing power and storage, fog nodes are unable to complete some UAV tasks. Consequently, in order to do these tasks, cloud resources are needed [7]. Heavy computing activities and latency-sensitive jobs can be offloaded from UAVs and partially processed on more resourceful platforms (i.e., fog and cloud systems) to alleviate these limits and obtain processing and communication requirements. While fog services offer low latency for UAV applications to meet the strict delay requirement, cloud services offer resource-intensive and scalable resources to meet computation demand (because fog nodes are closer to the UAVs). Different service capabilities (such as boosting processing and storage and lowering service latency) can be offered by merging fog and cloud computing models while keeping the UAV's resources (like its battery) at a reasonable level. In order to lower service latency and provide necessary resources and services instantly, UAV cooperation may also be taken into consideration.

As a result, a cooperative strategy for UAV applications is offered in this work in order to reduce service latency and provide the necessary resources and services instantly. For instance, the UAVs will work together to provide the necessary services, including processing power, low service latency, communication, and data storage, when one UAV needs more resources in a particular location. Additionally, this method makes use of cloud computing and fog capabilities, which enable certain UAV applications to be dynamically supported at various locations. Therefore, by optimizing the allocation of processing resources and communication needed by each UAV, task offloading decisions utilizing the Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model are created to lower the energy consumption of the complete proposed fog-cloud system. The key contributions to this work are outlined in the following.

- Create a productive architecture to look at UAV services and applications being offloaded into geographically dispersed fog-cloud environments.
- Create a cooperative UAV-Fog-Cloud plan to effectively meet UAV resource needs in real time and minimize service delay.
- Optimize UAV offloading choices using a fog-cloud architecture while taking networking and processing power usage into account.
- Utilizing a simulated environment, assess the effectiveness and suitability of the suggested collaborative offloading technique and compare the outcomes to those of other current strategies.

This work is arranged as follows for the remainder. In Section II, the relevant work is covered. Section III presents the contact layers of a cooperative UAV-fog-cloud system. In order to optimize the offloading of UAV applications into the UAV-fog-cloud system, the mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model design and its input parameters are introduced in Section IV. In Section V, the experimental setup is explained and the findings are analyzed. Section VI introduces the heuristic strategy for validating the MILP model. Section VII presents the final analysis and possible avenues for further investigation.

I. RELATED WORK

Reviewing recent scientific findings and their constraints regarding service latency, job offloading, and energy consumption is essential to comprehending UAV-enabled fog-cloud systems from a technology standpoint. As seen in Table I, an overview of these accomplishments is given in this part along with a comparison review of closely related work.

LATENCY OF UAV SERVICE AND TASK OFFLOADING

Using a UAV-assisted paradigm, UAVs serve as middlemen between ground-based consumers and MEC nodes by utilizing Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) servers [8]. This model shortens the time it takes for IoT consumers to receive offloaded task services by utilizing MEC's processing and storage capabilities. As a result, this would support cooperatively optimizing UAV job scheduling. UAVs are integrated with 5G mobile networks in [9] to decrease end-to-end latency and enhance communication dependability.

Reduced service delays and improved offloading have been attained by efficiently managing the network through the deployment of MEC-affiliated UAVs. An iterative algorithm was created by Zhou et al. [10] to improve service latency, task offloading, data transmission, UAV processing capacity, and UAV location. Additionally, for MEC services enabled by UAVs, a task-offloading algorithm (iTOA) has been developed [11]. Their approach uses a deep Monte Carlo tree algorithm to make educated judgments on offloading by analyzing the network's surroundings. This method outperforms the other methods in terms of service latency when compared to the greedy search and game theory methods.

ENERGY CONSUMPTION (PROCESSING AND NETWORKING)

Using the Markov Decision Process (MDP), a UAV-enabled MEC architecture was created to maximize work offloading and energy consumption [12].

UAVs were regarded as intelligent mobiles in their investigation. A block coordinate descent algorithm and successive convex approximation techniques were introduced in [13] for the purpose of improving data offloading depending on energy usage. By taking into account a single UAV, our method improved task offloading and energy consumption. Owing to the restricted processing power of UAVs, an offloading strategy built on the MEC architecture was presented in [14]. Their method involves the deployment of IoT devices to gather data from users on the ground, which is subsequently transmitted by UAVs to MEC servers situated on a private network for processing. The energy usage of UAV-enabled MECs was examined in [1] using an autonomous delivery network. A computational management system was also specifically designed to address MEC-based scheduling and task-offloading techniques. Together with dynamic resource allocation, their integrated solution includes static job offloading. Test findings show that the system can manage several UAV applications while using less energy.

The GESE system was proposed to integrate cloudlets on multiple UAVs in order to provide compute services at the edge of a network [15]. Researchers examined the performance of their proposed system to determine the impact of offloading computing tasks on energy efficiency. Du et al. [16] presented a UAV-based MEC model using Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA). Based on their model, task partitioning was optimized to reduce UAV energy consumption.

In an attempt to reduce computational complexity associated with UAV-assisted MEC, the successive convex approximation and lagrangian duality method were introduced in [17]. This approach minimizes the overall energy consumption, which include (computation, communication, and UAV energy). Furthermore, a UAV-assisted MEC system that provides computing services to IoT devices through the use of edge servers,

is presented in [18]. This proposed system minimizes its energy consumption by employing k-means clustering. Also, a UAV-enabled MEC system was proposed by Hu et al. [19], employing UAVs as flying MEC nodes. This approach minimized energy consumption by scheduling UAV computation resources for both UAV and ground-based users. Moreover, an optimization method for UAV-enabled MEC was developed in [20], which combined two layers of optimization. With the help of a removal agent, a differential evolution algorithm was proposed, and power consumption was successfully optimized with this approach. Li et al. [21] addressed the problem of IoT devices' energy consumption in UAV-enabled MEC networks. In their approach, optimizing communications and computing resource allocation have improved energy and offloading requirements.

COLLABORATIVE UAVS' TASK OFFLOADING FOR OPTIMIZING SERVICE LATENCY AND ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Recently, the use of UAVs as computational and communication platforms has attracted the attention of many researchers. Some recent works support the idea of collaborative UAVs, for example, a collaborative multi-UAV- assisted MEC system is proposed in [22]. As part of their approach, they studied issues related to service latency and energy minimization. Also, they have optimized offloading decisions, considering each UAV's computation resources and communication requests. Moreover, Chen et al. [23] and Ren et al. [24] introduced offloading methods to partially offload tasks between a cloud server and several edge nodes for collaborative execution. These methods improve service performance and use communication and computing resources more effectively. Further, Guo et al. [25] presented a delay-based workload distribution model. It obtains workload distribution between local edge nodes, nearby edge nodes, and cloud servers to reduce energy consumption and task delay for IoT-edge-cloud systems.

In addition, He et al.[26] proposed collaborative task offloading, considering energy consumption and battery power. They have developed an algorithm for collaborative task offloading to handle delay- sensitive tasks effectively. According to Liu et al. [27] a dynamic caching strategy was used to improve collaborative task offloading in MEC. To effectively reduce service delays, they proposed a multilayered computing strategy named Joint Task Offloading and Service Caching (JTOSC). As shown in the simulation results, the proposed strategy performs better in terms of service cache rate, offloading delay, and load balance than existing methods.

Cooperative task assignment is considered an NP-hard problem. In previous studies, the cooperative task assignment problem was formulated using mixed-integrated linear programming (MILP) [28], which achieved an optimal assignment solution. Rahbari et al. [2] proposed a rating method for swarm drones based on a federated learning strategy. The rating method continually computes drones' offloading events, considering current properties (e.g., energy consumption and communication latency). A novel system for MEC has been introduced in [29]. They have presented a genetic trajectory planning algorithm to operate IoT devices, using multiple UAVs.

Accordingly, traditional optimization methods are used to estimate the number of UAVs and their constructs to reduce flying distances and hence their communication latency and energy consumption. Liwang et al. [30] proposed a futures-enabled resource trading mechanism designed to facilitate fast and efficient resource allocation in edge computing-assisted UAV networks. The mechanism leveraged futures contracts to enable proactive resource trading between UAVs and edge computing servers. This approach aimed to anticipate future resource demands and efficiently allocate resources to minimize service latency, optimize task offloading decisions, and reduce energy consumption. Additionally, the authors in [31] introduced a graph-represented approach for computation-intensive task scheduling, leveraging the integration of air and ground vehicles in vehicular network (AGVN).

The solution involved formulating the task scheduling problem as a graph-based optimization problem, where nodes represent tasks and edges represent communication links between UAVs and vehicles. This approach aimed to minimize service latency and energy consumption while ensuring efficient task offloading and collaboration among UAVs. The authors in [32] proposed a novel approach that leverages edge-assisted UAV networks for intelligent mobile crowd sensing. They introduced task state information sharing mechanisms to enhance task scheduling and resource allocation, aiming to reduce service latency and optimize energy consumption. Also, Guo et al.[33] presented a novel solution for optimizing task offloading and resource allocation among multiple UAVs in advanced wireless communication networks, focusing on reducing service latency, optimizing energy consumption, and leveraging collaborative UAV capabilities. Based on the above review of related work, multiple approaches have been introduced with various objectives, such as reducing service latency, optimizing task offloading, and minimizing energy consumption.

Nevertheless, there are still some challenges due to the variable dynamics of networks and resource allocation, resulting in high service latency and energy consumption for performing tasks on UAVs.

It is important to note that the proposed approach shares similarities with the works discussed in [32] and [33] regarding their objectives. However, it offers several significant improvements compared to these approaches, listed as follows

Integration of Fog and Cloud Computing: While[32] focuses on edge-assisted UAV networks and [33] addresses resource allocation among multiple UAVs in wireless communication networks the proposed method integrates fog and cloud computing to overcome the limitations of UAVs' computing capabilities and optimize task offloading strategies. This integration allows for additional resource capacities as needed, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency and effectiveness of UAV applications.

Collaborative Offloading Strategy: In contrast to the methods described in [32] and [33], which primarily focus on optimizing task offloading and resource allocation among UAVs, the proposed method introduces a collaborative offloading strategy leveraging fog and cloud computing capabilities. This strategy aims to minimize UAVs' service latency and energy consumption by optimizing the allocation of computation resources (among UAVs, fog nodes, and cloud servers) and communication requested by each UAV

Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) Model: While [32] and [33] use different optimization techniques, the proposed method utilizes a MILP model for task offloading decisions. This model enables the reduction of energy consumption of the entire UAV-fog-cloud system by optimizing the allocation of computation resources and communication, thereby enhancing overall system efficiency.

Motivated by these considerations, a collaborative approach is proposed to enable smooth resource integration between local UAV devices and services, leveraging fog and cloud computing advantages and capabilities. Additionally, an optimization model is presented to minimize UAV service latency and energy consumption, considering different traffic loads and processing requirements when placing UAV applications in a UAV-fog-cloud architecture. It also allows offloading heavy tasks remotely to fog and cloud nodes to utilize their powerful services and effectively support UAV applications.

II.PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

As discussed in sections I and II, some UAV applications may need to be connected to the cloud in order to benefit from advanced services (e.g., auto-scaling resources, powerful processing, and data storage). However, connecting UAV applications to the cloud may have some limitations, as the cloud lacks support for some of the essential

requirements of UAV applications such as location awareness and mobility [29]. Also, when a task is submitted to the cloud, this may increase service latency as well as network energy costs [2]. Hence, it is necessary to enhance task offloading strategies in order to efficiently perform UAV applications. In order to overcome these limitations, fog computing enhances cloud architecture by providing distributed platforms located at the edge of the network and closer to geographically distributed UAVs [4]. It also provides monitoring, processing, and communication services to support certain UAV applications. However, since UAVs work independently to perform their applications, there is a need to develop a collaborative approach for UAVs to support real time task response with low latency.

FIGURE 1. The collaborative UAV-fog-cloud architecture.

Therefore, a collaborative approach is proposed to incorporate three layers, namely, the UAV layer, the fog layer, and the cloud layer, as illustrated in Fig. 1. These layers interact with each other to efficiently support UAV offloading decisions. In the following, each layer of the proposed system is described.

A. UAV LAYER

This layer provides a set of collaborative UAVs, equipped with processors, storage, and communication devices, and working as a flying fog node. Also, these collaborative UAVs can be allocated and reallocated to various locations where extra resources are needed to execute different UAV applications and services. Therefore, instead of immediately offloading UAV tasks to cloud or fog nodes, there are several features that can be provided by using collaborative UAVs [3], for example:

Rapid Deployment: UAVs can be quickly deployed to support critical and urgent operations at any location (e.g., accident detection and rescue in areas that are difficult for humans to reach).

Collaboration: Multiple UAVs can be allocated to easily support and satisfy specific application requirements.

Resource Elasticity: Multiple UAVs can be equipped with different resource capabilities (e.g., a temporary need for high processing or more storage).

B. CLOUD AND FOG LAYERS

Cloud computing is a fundamental enabler for the development of UAV applications. It provides on-demand services and large-scale computing resources (e.g., processing, storage, and networking) to meet the requirements of UAVs. However, cloud computing is a centralized design, which inspired researchers to establish distributed services as a cloud extension.

Therefore, Cisco introduced the fog computing paradigm in 2014 [34], which expands the usage of cloud resources to the edge of the network (proximity to users) to lower service latency for critical applications (e.g., driverless cars and UAV applications) [35]. Also, fog computing is widely distributed (geographically) and can provide networking, computing, and storage services among cloud data centers and end devices [28].

In light of the limited computing resources of UAV devices along with the massive amount of data generated by UAV applications, it is suggested that tasks requiring substantial computational resources will be performed on computing systems that have adequate computing resources (such as fog or cloud systems). Hence, both cloud and fog computing are models that deliver computational resources, where fog nodes provide partial computing with low service latency as well as location awareness to optimize the placement of UAV applications, while cloud servers provide substantial computing capability with energy-efficient processing and elastic resources [4]. These models will overcome processing capability issues and service response time (e.g., real time analysis) of UAV applications.

C. TELECOMMUNICATION NETWORKS

The telecommunication network can be divided into three layers [28], including core, metro, and access network layers. The core network, which usually refers to the Wide Area Network (WAN), is the backbone infrastructure of a telecommunication network, which provides interconnection of large areas (e.g., different cities). In addition, the core network extensively uses the Internet Protocol (IP) via Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) for its large capacity, scalability, and high bandwidth. The metropolitan region is usually covered by a Metro Area Network (MAN), which has a direct connection to the WAN network. Also, the MAN network infrastructure is operated by metro ethernet technology. This allows connectivity between the WAN network and UAVs that are located in the access network. The access network indicates a Local Area Network (LAN) that allows end-users to connect to the Internet from various locations. In this work, Passive Optical Networks (PONs) are used, and they are also recommended in the LAN network as a leading choice [36].

I. MILP MODEL DESIGN

The MILP model is a mathematical optimization technique aiming to find a maximum or minimum solution subject to linear constraints. MILP variables contain both integer and non-integer values, and the studies demonstrated MILP is efficient in optimizing telecommunications for both cloud and fog applications. For instance, researchers in [33] and [34] devised models to enhance the energy efficiency of the WAN network. Similarly, [36] concentrated on formulating an energy-efficient model to optimize application placement within cloud and fog architectures. This model considers diverse CPU workloads along with varying download rates. This section investigates the effectiveness of offloading UAV applications over a fog-cloud architecture using a cooperative approach based on the MILP optimization model. Additionally, this approach takes into account the three telecommunication network layers, where (LAN) is performed with UAVs, (MAN) with fog nodes, and (WAN) in the cloud. Furthermore, the proposed system architecture is described in terms of parameters and variables (see Tables II and III). UAV, fog, and cloud layers are included in the system architecture, as previously mentioned. In addition, a mathematical model (MILP) is presented to optimize UAV applications' offloading over a fog-cloud architecture, considering service latency and energy consumption of processing and networking.

I. THE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP, RESULTS, AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed models are critically evaluated in this section via simulation-based experiment. Also a Brief description environment setup and resources used is presented. This is followed by a detailed discussion of the results.

A. EXPERIMENT SETUP

This section covers performance metrics for evaluating results. To optimize energy consumption, network resource utilization, and service latency, the proposed approach is evaluated using a simulation environment. Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) can solve complex optimization problems within a set of linear constraints, where only a limited number of variables are required to be integers, while others can have non-integer values. . A CPLEX (IBM ILOG) optimization solver is used in the experiment environment to solve the MILP model. A desktop computer running Windows 10 OS has been used for the simulation experiment. It has a 3.4 GHz Intel Core i7 CPU and 16

GB RAM as well as 512 GB SSD storage. Fig. 2 illustrates the European national network used in this work, which models the Euro 28 topology. It consists of (100 UAVs in each

FIGURE 2. The European reference network topology (Euro 28topology).

city, 28 fog nodes covering all cities, 1 cloud server, and 62 bidirectional links - 600 km in length). In Table II, the data rate and MIPS required for each UAV task are distributed according to the heterogeneous computing capabilities of UAVs, fog nodes, and cloud server. Furthermore, each UAV executes different computational tasks (e.g., low, medium, and high processing requirements), as shown in Table IV. Based on the input parameters and variables (listed in Tables II and III), simulation experiments are conducted 50 times, and average values are calculated.

EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This subsection evaluates the performance of the proposed strategy (UAV-Fog-Cloud Execution) along with three different offloading strategies:

- UAV Execution: The tasks will be processed locally within the UAV resources or offloaded to another UAV if the workload exceeds the UAV's capabilities.
- Fog Execution: The tasks will be offloaded from UAV to any appropriately connected fog nodes.

- Cloud Execution: The tasks will be offloaded from UAV or fog nodes to a cloud server for remote processing.
- UAV-Fog-Cloud Execution (Proposed Strategy): The tasks will be handled locally for processing at the UAV layer or offloaded remotely (to other UAVs, fog nodes, or cloud server) based on the requested resources of the UAV applications and the hosted resource capabilities. Using the proposed strategy, the offloading decision can be made to minimize system overhead at the end.

In the following, the results of service latency and energy consumption for processing different UAV tasks relative to the above offloading strategies are discussed.

1) UAV'S SERVICE LATENCY

Fig. 3 presents the service latency versus the number of UAVs for four different offloading strategies (mentioned in section V, subsection B). According to the figure, the service time for all strategies is about the same for a small number of UAVs (e.g., under 20 UAVs). In contrast, the delay for UAV, fog, and cloud strategies increases rapidly with an increasing UAV count (e.g., over 20 UAVs), and the effectiveness of the proposed strategy was superior to UAV, fog, and cloud strategies by 15%, 30.7%, and 55%, respectively. Due to the increase in UAVs, some fog nodes are overloaded while others are underloaded, resulting in poor fog strategy performance. Unlike the proposed strategy, which can autonomously assign and execute tasks, the other offloading strategies do not take into account the multi-level (i.e., UAV, fog, and cloud layers) when executing tasks.

FIGURE 3: Service time versus the number of UAVs

Furthermore, Fig. 4 illustrates the amount of time (service latency) it takes to process computation tasks with different input data sizes. In a comparison of the four strategies, the curves indicate the amount of time and effort needed to implement each one. According to the figure, the data size significantly increases the overall time taken to complete/deliver the service. The proposed strategy has the lowest service latency compared to the other three strategies (i.e., UAV, fog, and cloud) by 15.38%, 35.29%, and 59.26%, respectively. Thus, the proposed strategy can however be adapted to execute computation tasks in the UAV layer, in the fog layer, or in the cloud layer, depending on which location is optimum to perform these tasks.

FIGURE 4. Service time using different input data sizes.

Fig. 5 shows the execution time of computation tasks using fog nodes with different capabilities. This figure illustrates how UAV and cloud execution strategies are not affected by fog nodes' capabilities, but the service time for fog execution strategy and the proposed strategy decreases as fog nodes' capabilities increase. Also, the proposed strategy performs better than other strategies. To justify that, in the proposed strategy, some UAV tasks are processed locally, while others are offloaded to fog nodes based on the offloading decision. Thus, increasing fog nodes' capabilities means more resources are assigned to UAVs, resulting in shorter execution times for the proposed strategy. In contrast, other standalone strategies (i.e., UAVs and cloud strategies) ignore this benefit.

FIGURE 5. Service time with different capabilities of fog nodes.

Finally, Fig. 6 shows the average service time of the four strategies for each type of application (shown in Table IV). The proposed strategy achieved the shortest service latency for all types of applications, while cloud execution had the longest service latency for all types of applications. Since cloud execution is geographically distant from its users, it takes a long time to execute. Thus, the proposed strategy selects the appropriate location (either in another UAV, fog, or cloud layers) based on the requested resources of the UAV applications.

FIGURE 6. Service time using different applications type

1) ENERGY CONSUMPTION (PROCESSING AND NETWORKING)

Fig. 7 illustrates the energy consumption of processing tasks using the four strategies with different numbers of UAVs. From this figure, it can be deduced that UAV numbers increase energy consumption exponentially. With a small number of UAVs (e.g., under 40 UAVs), there is no significant energy gap between all strategies. However, this gap is growing with increasing numbers of UAVs, and the proposed strategy achieves the lowest energy consumption compared to other strategies (i.e., UAV, fog, and cloud) by 5.7%, 13.16%, and 17.5%, respectively. It also shows that cloud and fog strategies exceed UAV strategies. Due to the fact that UAVs in all strategies compete for limited communication resources.

These resources are used to offload computation tasks to connected fog nodes or cloud server, where most energy is consumed during data transmission. No matter what offloading strategy is used (UAV, fog, cloud, or the proposed strategy), communication channel resources compete between UAVs and consume more energy during offloading. Nevertheless, the proposed approach reduces energy consumption significantly compared to cloud and fog strategies.

FIGURE 7. Energy consumption versus the number of UAVs

Likewise, Fig. 8 shows the energy consumption for processing computation tasks using the four strategies based on different input data sizes. According to this figure, with a small data size (less than 15 MB) almost all UAV, fog, and cloud strategies consume the same amount of energy, while the proposed strategy slightly outperforms them. However, when the data size increases, UAV, fog, and cloud strategies consume more energy than the proposed strategy by 3.3%, 7.37%, and 12%, respectively. This is due to the lengthening of communication times and the increasing size of data, which affects total energy consumption. Hence, by smartly adapting the proposed strategy to handle computation tasks, energy consumption can be reduced. In addition, it can be determined the most energy-effective decision (the best location to execute UAV applications).

FIGURE 8. Energy consumption using different input data sizes.

Figure 9 presents the energy consumption of processing UAV tasks using the four strategies relative to different fog node numbers. This figure shows that the UAV and cloud execution strategies are not affected by the number of fog nodes, while the other strategies (fog and the proposed strategies) continuously consume less energy when the number of fog nodes increases. Additionally, the proposed strategy enables lower energy consumption and better performance than the other strategies. Due to an increase in fog nodes, UAVs are assigned more resources (in the proposed strategy), which leads to a decrease in energy consumption, while the cloud strategy does not use fog nodes' resources.

FIGURE 9. Energy consumption with different numbers of fog nodes

I. THE VALIDATION OF THE MILP MODEL THROUGH A HEURISTIC APPROACH

In this section, an alternative method is introduced to validate the results of UAV application offloading generated by the proposed MILP model. However, addressing the optimization of UAV application offloading utilizing the MILP model to minimize service latency and power consumption is recognized as an NP-hard problem [28]. Due to the multiple possibilities of offloading locations ($L = 29$) in the scenario considered (including 28 fog nodes covering all cities, 1 cloud server, and 62 bidirectional links spanning 600 km), the MILP model faces significant challenges in finding the optimal with polynomial set.

The algorithm computes the total power consumption (PC) linked to offloading each UAV application $x \in app$ within its designated placement $O \subset R$, this would be based on the resource requirements of each UAV application type. Initially, a multi-hop heuristic approach is employed by the algorithm to distribute UAV applications through the access and core networks to target nodes d and s , thereby estimating the power consumption of these networks. Subsequently, the algorithm determined the best location (O') to host UAV applications and estimates the total power consumption (PC) of the fog- cloud architecture.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Most computation offloading approaches for UAV applications are based on a single-level architecture. Therefore, a collaborative UAVs approach assisted with a multi-level fog-cloud system is presented in this work. Also, service latency and energy consumption issues are investigated by optimizing offloading decisions, communications, and computing resource allocations over collaborative UAVs as well as fog-cloud environments. This helped to find the optimal location for the placement of UAV tasks for processing.

Additionally, mathematical modeling is provided to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach by comparing the results with other existing strategies (e.g., local and remote executions). From the results, it is clear that the proposed strategy (UAV-Fog-Cloud execution) is capable of reducing UAV's service latency by (15.38%, 35.29%, and 59.26%), and overall energy consumption of both processing and networking by (3.3%, 7.37%, and 12%) compared to other standalone strategies (i.e., UAV, fog, and cloud), respectively. A part of future work would include artificial intelligence and machine learning methodologies such as deep learning and reinforcement learning to handle the complexity of fog-cloud computing systems for enhancing UAVs' trajectories and task offloading decisions.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Almutairi, M. Aldossary, H. A. Alharbi, B. A. Yosuf, and J. M.H. Elmirghani, "Delay-Optimal Task Offloading for UAV- Enabled Edge-Cloud Computing Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 51575–51586, (2022), doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3174127.
- [2] D. Rahbari, M. M. Alam, Y. Le Moullec, and M. Jenihhin, "Fast and Fair Computation Offloading Management in a Swarm of Drones Using a Rating-Based Federated Learning Approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 113832–113849, (2021), doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3104117.
- [3] N. Mohamed, J. Al-Jaroodi, I. Jawhar, H. Noura, and S. Mahmoud, "UAVFog: A UAV-based fog computing for Internet of Things," in *2017 IEEE SmartWorld, Ubiquitous Intelligence & Computing, Advanced & Trusted Computed, Scalable Computing & Communications, Cloud & Big Data Computing, Internet of People and Smart City Innovation (Smart World/SCALCOM/UIC/ATC/CBDCom/IOP/SCI)*, (2017), pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1109/UIC-ATC.2017.8397657.
- [4] F. H. Rahman, S. H. S. Newaz, T.-W. Au, W. S. Suhaili, M. A. P. Mahmud, and G. M. Lee, "EnTruVe: ENergy and TRUst-aware Virtual Machine allocation in VEHICLE fog computing for catering applications in 5G," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 126, pp. 196–210, (2022), doi: 10.1016/j.future.2021.07.036.
- [5] E. Mustafa et al., "Reinforcement learning for intelligent online computation offloading in wireless powered edge networks," *Cluster Computing*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 1053–1062, Apr. (2023), doi: 10.1007/s10586-022-03700-5.
- [6] J. Chen, S. Chen, S. Luo, Q. Wang, B. Cao, and X. Li, "An intelligent task offloading algorithm (iTOA) for UAV edge computing network," *Digital Communications and Networks*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 433–443, Nov. (2020), doi: 10.1016/j.dcan.2020.04.008.

- [7] W. Ouyang, Z. Chen, J. Wu, G. Yu, and H. Zhang, "Dynamic Task Migration Combining Energy Efficiency and Load Balancing Optimization in Three-Tier UAV-Enabled Mobile Edge Computing System," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 2, p. 190, Jan. **2021**, doi: 10.3390/electronics10020190.
- [8] H. Guo and J. Liu, "UAV-Enhanced Intelligent Offloading for Internet of Things at the Edge," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 2737–2746, Apr. **(2020)**, doi: 10.1109/TII.2019.2954944.
- [9] J. Liu et al., "Reliability-Enhanced Task Offloading in Mobile Edge Computing Environments," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 13, pp. 10382–10396, Jul. **2022**, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2021.3115807.
- [10] M. Liyanage, F. Dar, R. Sharma, and H. Flores, "GEESE: Edge computing enabled by UAVs," *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, vol. 72, p. 101340, Apr. **(2021)**, doi: 10.1016/j.pmcj.2021.101340.
- [11] Y. Du, K. Yang, K. Wang, G. Zhang, Y. Zhao, and D. Chen, "Joint Resources and Workflow Scheduling in UAV-Enabled Wirelessly-Powered MEC for IoT Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 10187–10200, Oct. **2019**, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2019.2935877.
- [12] T. Zhang, Y. Xu, J. Loo, D. Yang, and L. Xiao, "Joint Computation and Communication Design for UAV-Assisted Mobile Edge Computing in IoT," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 16, no. 8, pp. 5505–5516, Aug. **(2020)**, doi: 10.1109/TII.2019.2948406.
- [13] Y. Liu, K. Xiong, Q. Ni, P. Fan, and K. Ben Letaief, "UAV-Assisted Wireless Powered Cooperative Mobile Edge Computing: Joint Offloading, CPU Control, and Trajectory Optimization," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 2777–2790, Apr. **2020**, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2019.2958975.
- [14] X. Hu, K.-K. Wong, K. Yang, and Z. Zheng, "UAV-Assisted Relaying and Edge Computing: Scheduling and Trajectory Optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 4738–4752, Oct. **(2019)**, doi: 10.1109/TWC.2019.2928539.
- [15] Y. Wang, Z.-Y. Ru, K. Wang, and P.-Q. Huang, "Joint Deployment and Task Scheduling Optimization for Large-Scale Mobile Users in Multi-UAV-Enabled Mobile Edge Computing," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 50, no. 9, pp. 3984–3997, Sep. **(2020)**, doi: 10.1109/TCYB.2019.2935466.
- [16] W.-T. Li et al., "Collaborative offloading for UAV-enabled time-sensitive MEC networks," *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, vol. 2021, no. 1, p. 1, Dec. **(2021)**, doi: 10.1186/s13638-020-01861-8.
- [17] Y. Chen, Z. Li, B. Yang, K. Nai, and K. Li, "A Stackelberg game approach to multiple resources allocation and pricing in mobile edge computing," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 108, pp. 273–287, **(2020)**, doi: 10.1016/j.future.2020.02.045.
- [18] J. Ren, G. Yu, Y. He, and G. Y. Li, "Collaborative Cloud and Edge Computing for Latency Minimization," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 5031–5044, **(2019)**, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2019.2904244.
- [19] M. Guo, L. Li, and Q. Guan, "Energy-Efficient and Delay-Guaranteed Workload Allocation in IoT-Edge-Cloud Computing Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 78685–78697, **(2019)**, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2922992.
- [20] C. He, R. Wang, and Z. Tan, "Energy-Aware Collaborative Computation Offloading Over Mobile Edge Computation Empowered Fiber-Wireless Access Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 24662–24674, **(2020)**, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2969214.
- [21] X. Liu, X. Zhao, G. Liu, F. Huang, T. Huang, and Y. Wu, "Collaborative Task Offloading and Service Caching Strategy for Mobile Edge Computing," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 18, p. 6760, Sep. **2022**, doi: 10.3390/s22186760.
- [22] M. Aldossary and H. A. Alharbi, "Towards a Green Approach for Minimizing Carbon Emissions in Fog-Cloud Architecture," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 131720–131732, **(2021)**, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3114514.
- [23] M. Asim, W. K. Mashwani, S. B. Belhaouari, and S. Hassan, "A Novel Genetic Trajectory Planning Algorithm With Variable Population Size for Multi-UAV-Assisted Mobile Edge Computing System," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 125569–125579, **(2021)**, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3111318.
- [24] M. Liwang, Z. Gao, and X. Wang, "Let's Trade in the Future! A Futures-Enabled Fast Resource Trading Mechanism in Edge Computing-Assisted UAV Networks," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 3252–3270, Nov. **(2021)**, doi: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3088657.
- [25] M. Liwang, Z. Gao, S. Hosseinalipour, Y. Su, X. Wang, and H. Dai, "Graph-Represented Computation-Intensive Task Scheduling Over Air-Ground Integrated Vehicular Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 3397–3411, Sep. **(2023)**, doi: 10.1109/TSC.2023.3270169.